

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO ENHANCE EFL STUDENTS' WRITING SKILLS

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Abstract. *In recent years, the use of new approaches and methods in language learning has become one of the requirements of the era. When it comes to innovative technologies and of course, it is necessary to mention the development of artificial intelligence (AI) . We can say that AI technologies have started a new stage of revolution in almost all fields. When it comes to writing skills, many EFL students consider this skill to be the most difficult and the one that requires great skill. We can give several reasons for this: lack of lexical resources, inability to use complex grammatical structures, punctuation errors and lack of ideas. As a result of the integration of AI technologies into education, several AI tools have emerged to solve these problems and achieve academic writing. This article discusses the problems that students face in writing skill . Namely, AI tools and their use. and research on the use of ChatGPT(Generative Pre-trained Transformer) in the educational process.*

Keywords: *ChatGPT, Grammarly, Quillbot, Ideamap, Hemingway Editor, Artificial Intelligence (AI), writing.*

Introduction. ChatGPT is a chatbot or artificial intelligence produced and introduced by OpenAI in November 2022. It has brought about several improvements in human life. It can be used to communicate, get answers to questions of interest, formulate or solve complex problems, and perform various similar tasks. Artificial intelligence technologies are developing at a rapid pace. People are using it not only in education but also in almost all fields, which ensures that many systems work accurately and with high quality. Today, many educational apps, including Khan Academy, are using AI effectively because it allows you to work with the learner individually. The learner can freely ask questions, get quick answers, and complete various exercises. AI provides several high-quality services for the educational process for both teachers and students.

Main part. The main part of learning a language is the skills of reading, writing, listening and speaking. Among these, the skills that language learners face the most difficulty are writing and reading. Because these two skills require the student's own

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opinion and worldview. Majority of EFL students consider writing to be more difficult and responsible. And they try to avoid it. It would be a mistake to simply order someone to write an essay from ChatGPT. This would lead to laziness. Several artificial intelligence-powered programs, such as Notion AI, AI Brainstorming and Idea Generation, and Ideamap, help students deepen their thinking skills and find new ideas and arguments. For example, ideamap provides the learner with a map that contains various ideas about a topic. Through this app or website, a student can collect various brainstorming ideas and organize them into a perfect essay. Instructors believe that the use of modern technologies in education is effective. This is also a very convenient method for students, because they can analyze themselves through AI without the support of any teacher. In this way, they can identify their strengths and weaknesses with the help of these programs, develop their skills in their own way, combining their own strategies, preferences and needs. The student not only learns to write through AI, but also learns stylistic elements.

In addition, during the writing process, students also encounter difficulties such as shallow grammatical knowledge, low vocabulary, and punctuation errors, plagiarism poor writing skills and lack of structure. For example, Quillbot is the most suitable tool for paraphrasing and summarizing. It helps to create perfect sentence structures for these requirements, providing different word options and phrases and finding the right one. In addition, Quillbot helps to detect plagiarism, corrects syntactic and punctuation errors in sentences. Through this application, students can achieve academic writing skills, coherence and fluency. There is plenty of research being done on how artificial intelligence can improve writing. For example, Indonesian researchers conducted a study with 30 students from Kalideres RPTRA and concluded that using AI technology is effective in improving writing skills. The students' pre-test score was 71.47 and post-test score was 81.23, which means that their scores improved after using ChatGPT. Forbes Advisor conducted a survey of teachers, according to which more than half of teachers believe positive effect of AI technologies, and 60% of educators use them in their workflow. The advancement of AI and technology allows students to explore various technological tools that support academic writing in English, helping them develop stronger writing skills. Each technological tool offers distinct features that assist students in producing academic English texts. Popular AI-driven tools provide automated feedback, corrections, and suggestion. They also gain valuable support that enhances their writing skills and ensures long-term improvement. As students' progress, their

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academic writing benefits from improved language proficiency, leading to higher-quality written work. Findings suggest that ChatGPT enhances language learning by simulating human-like interactions, creating a more engaging learning experience. Additionally, the study identified effective instructional methods and pedagogical strategies to maximize the educational benefits of ChatGPT (Zulfikasari et al., 2024).

Conclusion. The use of revolutionary technologies in the educational process is becoming a daily requirement. The devices provided by artificial intelligence have led to significant changes in education. Sal Khan (Founder of Khan Academy) believes that AI can revolutionize education by providing personalized learning experiences tailored to each student's needs, helping them learn at their own pace. Andreas Schleicher (OECD Director for Education and Skills) states that AI can reduce the workload of teachers by automating tasks like grading, administrative work, and even providing real-time feedback, allowing educators to focus on student engagement.

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